

FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRY NETWORKS

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Annotation: Radical change of innovation activities in enterprises based on market requirements, introduction and modernization of modern and promising forms of management, effective use of modern information systems and technologies are the main requirements of today and the main condition for survival of the enterprise in the conditions of market competition.

Keywords: idea, scheme and drawings, practice, product, service, processes, innovation.

The development of innovative activities has become a generally accepted direction of effective development of humanity. Its pace is growing rapidly, and the scale of innovation is increasing. In this direction, significant results have been achieved in Japan, the USA, Germany and other similar countries, which are developing rapidly based on their great innovative achievements. It should be noted that innovative activities in these countries are supported by state and local government bodies. The experience of developed countries has shown that rapid growth of innovation cannot be ensured without such support.

In fact, the experience of developed countries shows that stabilization of industrial enterprises, stable growth of industrial production is achieved by transitioning the economy to the path of innovative development based on the creation of modern intensive technologies, the wide implementation of the results of scientific research and development in the field of production of high-tech products.

To study the international and local developments of modern equipment and technologies in Uzbekistan, to form annual and medium-term programs for the application of modern technologies to production on this basis, to form a set of orders for local applied scientific research and development, as well as to place them, to apply the results of applied scientific research and development to the practice of the enterprise implementation is envisaged.

Also, to introduce high-efficiency modern innovative technologies for the processing of fruits and vegetables, meat, milk and other agricultural food raw materials in our republic, for these purposes, first of all, to attract direct investments of strategic foreign investors, various innovation services, the task of expanding new means of communication is set. It should be noted that it is important to analyze the implementation of these decisions and identify trends in it. But before the analysis, let's clarify the concepts of "innovation" and "innovation activity".

Innovative activity can be understood as any activity related to innovation. In a narrow sense, innovative activity includes social production, its composition, product sales and management processes. In most countries, innovative activity covers more narrow areas - the process of assimilation of innovation by industry, including techniques and technologies, and in rare cases, methods of production organization and management. The activities that make up the content of innovative activity include practical research, development (experimental design

work), and the introduction of new technology into production. The first two stages are aimed at justifying the possibilities of practical use of scientific and technical achievements in production. Implementation is the process of implementing capabilities.

The results of the developments are specific solutions related to the tools and equipment being created. Therefore, innovative activities can be understood as all types of activities (production, service, etc.) related to the creation of new things.

It should be noted that innovative activities are mainly carried out by research institutions, higher education institutions (HEIs), design organizations, industrial enterprises and other organizations. Figure 3.1.1 shows that in 2007-2014, the number of construction organizations, research institutes and other organizations decreased, and on the contrary, the number of R&D, industrial enterprises increased.

It can be concluded that the number of enterprises engaged in innovative activities in the field of small business and the innovations created by them is increasing. This leads to an increase in the value of the innovative unit. All this has a positive effect on the economic and financial activity of small businesses.

It should be noted that most of the innovative goods, works and services created in our republic belong to the industrial sector.

In fact, if we look again at the composition of organizations engaged in innovative activities, even if the share of industrial enterprises engaged in innovative activities in the total number of enterprises engaged in this activity is small (as of 2014, this indicator was 2.9 percent), developed by them we can see that the share of innovative goods, works and services is high. In particular, by the end of 2014, 88% of the innovative goods, works and services created on the republic scale corresponded to industrial enterprises

This directly leads to an increase in the demand for the created labor force. In particular, the amount of value created per worker is high in the industrial sector. In particular, the value of each job created in the industry was 97.7 million soums, while in the service and agricultural sectors, this figure was 25.9 million soums. soums and equaled 21.6 million soums. That is, this indicator in industry is 3.7 and 4.5 times higher than in service and agricultural sectors, respectively.

If we analyze this indicator by industrial sectors, the main share goes to electrical engineering (652.1 million soums), mechanical engineering (461 million soums) and chemical and petrochemical industries (442.7 million soums). This is natural, because it is precisely in these sectors that products with high value are created. Construction (49 million soums), food (37.6 million soums), textiles (36 million soums), furniture making (25.8 million soums), leather industry; 88% transport and communication; 9% sales; 1% construction; 1% agriculture; 1% can be seen in footwear (23.9 million soums).

These indicators show that the innovative potential of industrial enterprises in our republic is high. At the same time, research shows that the industry has great opportunities for further development of innovative activities. In order to fully and effectively use them, it is necessary to overcome the existing problems in this area.

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